

SEPTEMBER
2022

**RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING CRITICAL
CATALOGING IN THE GoTRIPLE PLATFORM**

Version 1.1 – Draft
PUBLIC

H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019
Grant Agreement 863420

The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863420

Disclaimer- “The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the TRIPLE consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Project Acronym:	TRIPLE
Project Name:	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
Grant Agreement No:	863420
Start Date:	1/10/2019
End Date:	31/03/2023
Contributing WP	2
WP Leader:	Institute of the Literary Research Polish Academy of Sciences
Deliverable identifier	
Contractual Delivery Date: 31/12/2022	Actual Delivery Date: 31/12/2022
Nature: Report	Version:
Dissemination level	PUBLIC

Revision History

Version	Created/Modifier	Comments
0.0	Magdalena Wnuk	writing of the content
1	Svitlana Tarasova	writing of recommendations

Table of Contents

Recommendations for Implementing Critical Cataloging in the GoTriple Platform	1
Publishable Summary	3
1 Introduction	4
2 The literature review	5
3 Workshop sessions and conclusions	5
3 Recommendations	7

Publishable Summary

The aim of this document is to present *critical cataloging* as a perspective for the GoTriple discovery service controlled vocabulary, its development, maintenance and user engagement strategies. It summarises a 5-month process that included the preparation of a literature review and workshop scenario and organisation of two national workshops on critical cataloging for Polish and Ukrainian stakeholders. The main results of these activities form the basis for the recommendations for the GoTriple team regarding implementing critical cataloging as a research perspective relevant to creation of the platform's multilingual vocabularies as well as a method for improving discoverability of its resources. The document briefly presents the subsequent stages of the activity: the literature review, the workshop sessions and the recommendations stemming from the latter.

The GoTriple platform is a dedicated service of the OPERAS research infrastructure and will become a strong service in the [EOSC marketplace](#). It helps social sciences and humanities (SSH) research in Europe to gain visibility, to be more efficient and effective, to improve its reuse within the SSH and beyond, and to dramatically increase its societal impact. The European Commission finances the project under the Horizon 2020 framework with approx. 5.6 million Euros for a duration of 42 months.

1 Introduction

The knowledge organisation system used in the GoTriple platform is based on controlled vocabularies and their specific type: subject headings. A controlled vocabulary is a tool that helps standardise information and ensures persistent representation by promoting consistency of data across records, collections and entities, which is particularly important for discovery services. The most important function of a controlled vocabulary is to cluster variant terms and synonyms and connect concepts in an order. In specific, a controlled vocabulary is an organised closed set of concepts – words and phrases – categorising information collected in a concrete database, such as a library computer catalogue or an online discovery service ([Harpring 2010](#)). Subject headings are controlled vocabularies structured in a hierarchical way. The hierarchy derives from the meaning associated with the described object and the information it contains. Due to social and cultural change, as well developments in science and humanities controlled vocabularies often carry bias, become obsolete and inaccurate.

Discussions and community feedback at the hackathon and TRIPLE conference (Nov. 2021) pointed to the need of a more critical and Europe-focused approach to outdated terms which could be considered culturally insensitive or even offensive. In February-June 2022 IBL PAN team prepared a literature review on the subject of critical cataloging and organised two online workshops with practitioners and researchers with a purpose to provide guidelines for GoTRIPLE on applying critical perspective for its vocabularies. In the next sections we will provide main conclusions and recommendations coming from completing those tasks.

2 The literature review

Critical cataloging is an interdisciplinary research movement that analyses stereotypes, social and cultural prejudices as well as obsolete or out-of-date information embedded in knowledge organisation systems. Its purpose is not only to identify these biases and distortions, but also to propose solutions aimed at creating the most impartial knowledge organisation systems possible. It has been developing mainly in North America since the 1970s and grown tremendously in the last 30 years (Watson 2020) with several literature reviews being published since the 1990s. (Olson and Schlegl 1999, Kim 2003, Gardner 2011, Speller 2007, Watson 2020). At the moment the so called “critcat movement” is a growing community publishing primarily in various American and British journals and exchanging knowledge through social media. More information about the critical cataloging activists you may find on the blogs: <http://critlib.org/about/> and <https://cataloginglab.org/welcome/>.

The critique of cataloguing and specific knowledge organisation systems has been developing in relation to the criticism of colonialism and the rise of postcolonial studies (Biswas 2018, Duarte and Belarde-Lewis 2019, Drabinski 2019, Fernandez 2018, Schroeder and Hollister 2014). As of lately another important context was provided by technological advancements and projects engaging user experience approaches to cataloguing. The thorough review of the academic debate in the field (a report is an attachment to this document) led us to distinguish six main topics discussed by the authors:

1. Ethnicities and race.
2. Cultural differences.
3. Space and geopolitics.
4. Gender and queer.
5. History and memory.
6. User centred approach.

Papers are often devoted to the critical review of Library of Congress Subject Headings – a controlled vocabulary recognised as a standard one up until today and used also for the GoTriple vocabulary structuration. This way reviewing those papers should be a good start for studying problems and challenges which should be taken into consideration during the process of adjusting the LCSH structure and concepts to the GoTriple needs. Various topics and concepts have been already analysed and some of the conclusions are relevant also for the European audiences. In the literature review report we summarised the most important findings and papers.

3 Workshop sessions and conclusions

The workshops took place on Zoom on 14th and 15th June 2022. They were conducted with the experts and practitioners from two countries: Poland and Ukraine in their respective national

languages. There was no open call for participants, since the number of places was limited and the goal was to gather experts and specialists in specific fields.

The theme of the workshops were minority literatures and cultures, therefore among the participants apart from librarians, bibliologists and catalogers were researchers, such as historians, sociologists and ethnographers. The Polish workshop focused specifically on the Roma languages, culture and literature and their representation in the controlled vocabularies of various libraries. The Ukrainian workshop put into focus actual ethnic issues (literature of Boiki, Lemki, Hutsuls and other minorities and its identification), folklore questions (Cossack songs and their motives) as well as historical points (the Second World War and its representation in catalogues due to political decisions).

The workshops took 5,5 hours (Polish) and 4 hours (Ukrainian). They were organised according to a common scenario, however, some modifications were implemented due to specificity of the participants and the timeframe of the workshop. The detailed programme of the critical cataloguing workshop for the GoTriple platform is as follows:

Programme (up to 6 hours with breaks)

Session 1

Introduction to the controlled vocabularies. (1 h)

1. Controlled vocabulary of GoTriple presentation (30-40 min)
2. Other controlled vocabulary/ies presentation (20 min)

Hands on activities in groups: why do we need the vocabularies? (1 h)

Session 2

Critical cataloging: objectives, methods and examples (1 h)

1. #Critcat movement in the USA and Canada (30 min)
2. Critical cataloging: local examples (30 min)

Hands on activities: finding and solving local examples (1 h)

Session 3

Critical cataloging for the GoTriple platform: discussion and recommendations (up to 1 h).

The Polish workshop featured hands-on activities in both sessions, whereas the Ukrainian one used the hands-on activities designed for session 2. It was previously discussed as an acceptable scenario,

since according to the workshop's objectives, the second activity should be considered crucial as it refers to critical review of selected concepts. Both hands-on activities regarded the updated and real cases. During the workshops the participants referred to catalogues of the Library of Congress as well as national libraries.

4 Recommendations

1. The majority of works and discussions on critical cataloguing take place in North America (USA and Canada). What we need is European perspective on the minority languages, differences in meanings between similar concepts, epochs or historical events in European knowledge organisation systems, Americanisation or other impacts on classifications and subject headings that are subjected to critical cataloguing. The social sciences and humanities, to which the GoTriple is dedicated, may play a special role here, since languages, ethnicities and cultural changes are the top topics of their research.

The GoTriple platform and its vocabulary can provide knowledge on those differences and ambiguities inscribed into European national catalogues interpreting the same historical events, phenomena, cultural heritage and other objects of humanist research. Organising an international event devoted to critical cataloguing of European vocabularies could be a start for such a debate to develop and engage various disciplinary experts and researchers.

2. There is a need to organise national interdisciplinary as well as expert seminars on selected topics which could bring up issues and help improve inadequate concepts' structure and key words. In some countries people who are professional librarians may not be aware of the terms of critical cataloguing, especially with controlled vocabularies, as their study program may not include it as in the case of Ukraine.

The GoTriple team has provided a scenario for a critical cataloguing workshop including hands-on activities for the participants (it is an attachment to this document). A workshop can be organised by any party in the respective national community of librarians or researchers interested in reviewing knowledge organisation systems and developing multilingual controlled vocabularies.

3. Engaging the GoTriple users into the process of reviewing and improving the GoTriple controlled vocabulary is not only an inspiring idea but it is also in line with a growing trend in the field of librarianship studies and cataloguing to include users' perspective in the construction of vocabularies.

The GoTriple team can implement a review mechanism for the vocabulary based on the users' activities on the platform. Users' search phrases and keywords, which are not covered

by the GoTriple vocabulary, could be reviewed and added by the decision makers in the Triple Consortium.

4. It would be useful to provide a feedback mechanism through which users could communicate with catalogers suggesting changes to the vocabulary. The Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) as the one responsible for world adopted subject indexing language has a practice of proposals for additions and changes that are looked through by the Policy, Training, and Cooperative Programs Division (PTCP). If they approve them, then an approved list is published ([Process for Adding and Revising Library of Congress Subject Headings \(loc.gov\)](#)). The list of already approved proposals is [Subject Heading Approved Monthly Lists \(classweb.org\)](#). Lists are represented monthly since July 15, 2011. As a follow-up to the Polish workshop, a similar form was suggested to be implemented by the National Library of Poland. The IBL PAN team will collaborate on this matter further with representatives of the library's cataloguing team.

For the GoTriple platform providing users with such a tool seems both feasible and along with the platform's objectives of openness and diversity. It can become a part of the discovery service and be accessible from the research results landing pages. It could be based on the Google form implemented by the Cataloging Lab on their site: <https://cataloginglab.org/suggest-a-heading/>

If you have multiple suggestions, please fill out the form once for each suggestion, unless the terms are very closely related (like, for example, "HIV-positive persons" and "HIV-positive women").

You can [view headings that have been submitted](#) via this form.

The image shows a screenshot of a web form titled "Suggest an LCSH". The form has a blue header bar with the title. Below the title, there is a text block that says "To view previously submitted headings, visit <http://cataloginglab.org/suggested-headings>". Below this is a user profile section showing the email "magdalena.wnuk@ibl.waw.pl (nieudostępniony)" and a link "Przełącz konto". There is also a small icon of a person. Below the profile section is a text input field with the question "What term are you suggesting be added or revised?". Below the input field is a label "Twoja odpowiedź" followed by a horizontal line representing the input area.

5. It would be useful if published datasets were linked, for example concepts in the LCSH or RAMEAU link to similar concepts in other catalogues built in other natural languages. That would be helpful for expert users who could easily compare classifications.

For instance, during the workshop Polish scholars found out that RAMEAU had a larger vocabulary for Romani people than LCSH or Polish National Library catalogue. The same situation was mentioned during the Ukrainian workshop concerning the examples of folklore Cossacks songs and motives. They are usually considered as pheasant ones in LCSH and Ukrainian National Library catalogues whereas in Lviv region there are regional electronic volumes of folk subject headings for this music that apply a wider vocabulary. The catalogues were made on the NGO initiatives of the Lviv Region.

For starters the GoTriple can provide such case studies as a part of educational material aimed at improving users' skills in methods of critical cataloguing as well as their awareness of knowledge organisation.

6. It is purposeful to analyse ethnic groups and their concepts more attentively and to focus on them whilst creating controlled vocabularies, that will lead to the full cultural layout to be seen in cataloguing. In the case of ethnic studies in Europe, especially those concerning marginalised groups, the insight from both researchers as well as members of those groups is crucial.

In European countries, such as Ukraine, and in multinational state entities, ethno-national problems have a specificity that extends to social memory which is reproduced in literature. Inclusion of ethnic minorities in the general national historical canon leads to certain complications of categorical status, associated with different influences and significance of these communities for national history and culture. The place of different ethnic groups in the collective memory of various European nations and ethnic groups depend on many factors: population size, place of settlement, ethnic kinship etc.

During the discussion on Romani subject heading the participants of the workshop taking place in Poland noticed mistakes in the classification of different Romani groups in Europe and the lack of concepts, such as Romaphobia.

During the Ukrainian workshop Ukrainian subject headings describing ethnic minority groups (Boikos, Hutsuls, Lemkos) were discussed. Ethnographers traditionally divide Rusyns into 4 subgroups - Subcarpathian Rusyn, Lemkosv, Boykosv and Hutsuls but those divisions are not easy to draw and therefore cultural heritage of those groups is difficult to classify. Participants pointed out mistakes and misconceptions about the ethnic literature terms and concepts for categorising new types of minority literatures.

The GoTriple team could learn from those examples and critically review these concepts in the GoTriple vocabulary in order to implement the most accurate solutions.

7. Developing advocacy strategies targeted at partners in national communities is another possible direction to take.

One of the biggest problems at this stage, based on the Ukrainian workshop is that terminological systems of many fields have not yet found their embodiment not only in a systematised presentation within controlled vocabularies, but also in traditional

terminological dictionaries. In Ukraine only a part of descriptors is included into the digital version of catalogues while a part of them is still left on paper. The newly added or edited descriptors may play an important role in the search of information, especially its update when it is spoken about such fields as economy, politics, history etc.

It is to the GoTriple team's vivid interest that such catalogues are digitised fully. Therefore developing advocacy practices and close collaboration with the GoTriple data providers - libraries and repositories, can be fruitful for the platform's development.

8. Creation of the GoTriple digest could include a critical cataloguing subsection regarding controversial concepts in the GoTriple vocabulary and other systems. This would complement the creation of the user-oriented online form for suggesting changes to the vocabulary (see point 4). Local and national libraries should be added to such a newsletter. Historians, anthropologists, ethnologists, linguists and other interested scholars should be targeted in order to encourage them to take part in vocabulary development.